
USING ELECTRONIC HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT FOR ORGANIZATIONAL EXCELLENCE-CASE STUDY AT SOCIAL SECURITY CORPORATION - JORDAN

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Abstract:

This study aimed to know the role of electronic human resource management on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan. In order to complete this study, a questionnaire was prepared and distributed to (97) middle and senior management levels in the institution, from which (82) valid questionnaires were recovered for analysis.

The study concluded with some results, the most: Social Security Corporation- Jordan use electronic human resource management at high rates, organizational excellence also high, there is a significant statistical effect of electronic human resource management on organizational excellence as a whole and on all its indicators in Social Security Corporation- Jordan. At the end researcher recommended Social Security Corporation to expand using electronic human resource management at all levels and functions of the corporation, reinforce exploiting electronic human resource management in organizational excellence with all its areas, and aware employees at Social Security Corporation about how to achieve organizational excellence by adopting electronic human resource management applications.

Keywords: Electronic Human Resource Management; Organizational Excellence; Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

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1. Introduction

The emergence of new and digital technology and its multiple uses across all aspects of life, increase the demand for technology with a view towards acquisition and utilization of these new technologies (Alraja&Malkawi, 2015). Technology has become the one essential element in the production processes and in providing various services all over the world (Malkawi, 2017).

The introduction of Information and communication technologies (ICTs) is a real revolution in the world of management, transforming traditional administrative services and business into e-business, protects the administrative entity, improves its performance and optimizing the use of services at high quality. The application of ICTs in Management has a strategic importance, contributing to support streamline administrative procedures, enables departments to plan

efficiently and effectively to benefit from business requirements, accelerate and facilitate decision-making, and provide quality of services with high technical standards to keep up with the times.

On the other hand, the HR strategy plays an important role in organizations by: increasing employee performance, reducing production costs, increasing productivity, improving customer service and increasing customer satisfaction (Durra& Al-Sabbagh, 2008, p. 114), it becomes obligatory for human resource function to meet the current challenges to generate organisational value. So, human resource departments have been forced to be strategic, flexible, and adjusted to customer requirements in a changing environment. When considering the fact that the demand for capable talents has become greater, technological innovations such as E-HRM are seen as a key for success. Also, increasing internal demands have inforced the implementation of E-HRM to design and deliver HR efficiently. Therefore, the use of technology is seen a suitable way for HR to create strategic sustainable value (Mäkinen, 2013).

2. Need of the Study

Now a days we ca not do business in public or private sector without using new technology and systems, this why researcher integrating ICTs in the studt, therefor study will highlight on electronic human resource management, its benefits, challenges and its role in organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan. This study considered one of few studies about one of important institutions in Jordan, which has a responsibility for a broad spectrum of Jordanian society future. It sheds light on the level of exploiting new technologies in this Corporation; especially at human resource function to deal with new updates and expand their work in environment suffer from poor economic conditions. If we know the role of this Corporation in managing and investing the amount of money gathered from subscribers for future, studies and legislation should be conducted and put in place to ensure this, in light of the erosion of income of citizens and the difficult economic conditions as a result of the conditions in the middle east. So studies like this can open horizons for Social Security Corporation through new technology applications specially E-HRM to survive and grow with the capabilities of E-HRM has the capability in improving organizational efficiency, effectiveness, and leverage the role of human resources as a strategic business partner to achieve excellence .

3. Literature Review

3.1. Electronic Human Resource Management

Electronic-management defined as a strategic approach of managing dynamic and future organizations depending on a technology-based system. It is a strategic approach, starts with vision and mission. It stresses the value obtained by the organization through IT capabilities (Malkawi, Alraja, and Hamadnah, 2013). Al-Salami (2008) defines e-management as “the process of automating all administrative functions and activities based on all necessary information technology to achieve the objectives of the new management in reducing paper usage, simplifying procedures, eliminating routine, and fast and accurate execution of tasks and transactions”. According to Amiri "Electronic management is the administrative process based on the potential of the Internet and business networks to plan, direct, and control the resources and core

competencies of the organization and others without borders, in order to achieve the goals" (Amiri, 2008).

The importance of e-management lies in its ability to deliver efficient, fast, and effective services to individuals, governmental, and non-governmental institutions, and their ability to cope with the tremendous development of information systems and the growing technological revolution. This is a prerequisite for the progress of the institutionalized communities and organizations. Therefore organizations obliged to adopt electronic management applications in the achievement of functions serve employees and the beneficiaries of their services alike (Shuai, Ahlam, 2016).

The importance of e-management also lies in its ability to cope with the qualitative and quantitative development of information technologies and systems. In addition, e-management is a strong response to the challenges of the 21st century, in which it must be able to deal efficiently and effectively with different variables (Masood, 2008).

Elements of electronic management (Academy of Pharmaceutical Education and Training 2012):
Basic elements of E-management are:

- Paperless management: The electronic archive consists of e-mail, directories, electronic notebooks, voice messages and automated follow-up applications (David, 2009).
- No time no place: The mobile phone and the new international telephone (Teledisk), electronic conferences and teleworking through virtual institutions continue 24 hours continuously, the idea of night and day, summer and winter are ideas no longer have a place in the new world (Laudon, 2016).
- Management with dynamic organizations: It works through network and smart institutions that rely on knowledge creation and dissemination (Malkawi, Alraja, and Hamadnah 2013).

Electronic Human Resource Management defined as the use of ICTs, Internet and Intranet in the organization to achieve the administrative work of human resources electronically, to provide services to its customers in the least time, effort, cost and high quality (Nasurdin, 2011). Wyatt also defines it as the application of technology that enables managers and employees to directly access human resources management and other organization services for communication, performance appraisal, team management, knowledge management and education or any other administrative purposes (Foster, 2008, p. 2).

The challenges facing human resources management are so deep and comprehensive that the profession itself is threatened. Some see it as obsolete and have no place in the future without changing and accommodating the challenges facing organizations in general. The most important challenge is the ICTs revolution, which has enormous implications for the human resources function, means radical changes in all human resources functions and activities, and the support and implementation of the Organization's strategic plans. In the era of the end of the concept of secure employment and transformation into a secure profession, changing organizational structures, reducing employment due to automation and technology, and moving towards the knowledge economy; the concept of electronic human resources management has emerged. To keep it as a function, flexible in its response to changes, and play its role in serving the strategic objectives of the organizations (Amunah, 2009).

In this regard, we have to differentiate between E-HRM and human resources information systems. HRIS directed towards the HRM itself. And users of these systems are mostly human resource managers for the purpose of developing the services provided to the organization, While E-HRM is the target category for those who are outside human resources management, whether they are managers or employees for online use by all employees of the organization (Academy of Pharmaceutical Education and Training (2012). E-HRM has the ability to improve organizational efficiency and leverage the role of (HR) as a strategic business partner.

Types of E-HRM (<http://businessjargons.com/e-hrm.html> Business Jargons A Business Encyclopedia):

- Operational E-HRM, which concentrates on the operational level of HR such as personal data and payroll.
- Relational E-HRM concerned with supporting business processes (selection, recruitment, etc.)
- Transformational E-HRM, which concerns with human resource strategies and activities such as knowledge creation and management.

Researchers defined many activities for E-HRM, for the purposes of this research we concentrated on the most important activities (Tan, 2011) (Alsairafi, 2009):

- Electronic Selection and recruitment: Use of electronic tools and techniques in the selection and recruitment processes, with the aim of ensuring that all procedures carried out according to the plans and regulations established and to ensure that the best competencies are obtained at the lowest cost. Now a day's most companies usually hire candidates using internet.
- Electronic compensation: Using electronic applications for compensation management to gather, process, store, analyze, and distribute compensation data and information to anyone at anytime, with the ability to access to this information also from anyone at anytime.
- Electronic learning and development: Using the internet and intranet for providing the data, information and online modules necessary for the process of training of working forces, implementation and evaluate the results of training, then provide monitoring mechanisms that ensure the effectiveness of training process.
- Electronic performance management: depending on web based technology to evaluate employee and organization performance.
- Human resources planning: it is defined as the development of a program that shows the need of the corporation from workers with the classification of its needs in terms of skills and disciplines required the required number of each type of specialization, and the time when such competencies should be available. Planning in the field of human resources necessary for the efficiency of the performance of the corporation by providing appropriate numbers of specializations appropriate to the completion of the plan established by the corporation in a timely manner (Al-Masri, 2004).

3.2. Organizational Excellence

The excellence management considered from the modern concepts defined by administrative thought, thanks to its emergence to the emergence of organizations took on the task of searching for the best ways to improve the performance of organizations and development and access to

levels to satisfy the various parties. The most famous of these organizations European Organization for Quality (EFQM), the Japanese, Organization for Quality (Prix Deming), And the (American Malcolm Baldrig) model of excellence (Rasheed, 2004). The main purpose of management in any organization is to achieve excellence in all its activities and achieve unprecedented results. This can only be achieved by supporting innovation, development and continuous improvement, and benefiting from previous experiences and practices in a manner that makes all decisions and policies of the organization unique (Belker, 2016). This has made the management of excellence an inevitable necessity in an accelerated environment in all its variants.

(Salmi, 2002) defined excellence as a state of managerial innovation and organizational excellence that achieves unprecedented levels of performance and implementation of production, marketing, financial and other processes in order to achieve excellence over competitors and satisfy customers and all stakeholders. While (Macgregor, 1994) defined organizational excellence as any act or activity of any person that enforces and strengthens the achievement within the organization and includes the elements of the work forces that constitute the structure of the organization. Whereas (Eskild& Anders, 1999) defined it as the overall method to work that leads to the balanced satisfaction of (organization clients, staff, and community), thereby increasing long-term success at work. According to (Glegeous, 1997) excellence organization is recognized the organization that consistently outperforms global best practices in accomplishing its work, and connects with its customers with the relationships of interaction and support. (Mcgregor 1994) defines organizational excellence as "every act or activity of every person that strengthens achievement within the organization and includes many of the work forces that constitute the structure of the organization."

The importance of organizational excellence stems from the ability of organizations to shape the forces that support excellence in organizations by achieving rapid change rates, achieving unlimited competition, and preserving the place and organizational status (labor, organizational culture, and organizational structure), then the growing sense of quality, and the ability to employ technology in information and creativity. The organizations consider that the objective of the process of organizational excellence is to develop a strong and capable work force and have the ability to produce services and goods that exceed the internal and external expectations of the consumer and achieve their desires and identify them. In addition, focus on the service or product maker to develop awareness of the goal of the organization, and by unleashing the energies of creativity and innovation, and not linked to restrictive policies and procedures. Then provide flexible leadership to guide, motivate, and communicate with him, where the workforce is considered a professional forces and human capital reliable on them in the process of creativity and innovation and achieve excellence if managed well (Khalida, 2016).

Researchers have identified a number of benefits to be gained from adopting organizational excellence:

- Provide the basis on which the organization can be developed.
- Provide an integrated and coordinated way to achieve tangible results.
- Identification of mutual dependencies and mutual relations between management areas.
- Reduce activities that do not add value.
- Provide a benchmarking program to measure performance.
- Provide a platform for long-term organizational success.

- Supplement other excellence programs.
- Increase business value.
- Provide a good return on investment.

Researchers identified multiple models and dimensions through which organizational excellence is measured: leadership, planning, customers, employees, business processes, resource management, suppliers, partners, etc. (Chatterjee, 2016) (Alsalabe ET. Al., 2017), However, according to (Harrington, 2004) upper management must simultaneously manage five key organizational Excellence elements, if an organization is to succeed. For the purposes of this study researcher adopted these Harrington five indicators to measure dependent variable (organizational excellence). Learning how to manage them together is the key to success in achieving organizational excellence. The five elements are:

- Process management: represents the activities and capabilities of transforming input into output that meets the customers' performance and quality requirements. Management in excellent organizations requires each natural work team (or department) to improve (refine) the processes that it uses. Refining the process is an ongoing activity.
- Change management: Intended and planned intervention to bring about growth and move from an existing status to a target one to achieve specific goals within a clear and common vision between the leadership and the staff of the organization.
- Project management: Application of skills, knowledge, techniques and tools to project activities to meet project requirements (Schwalbe, 2014).
- Knowledge management (KM) is a collection of systematic approaches to help knowledge and information flow between and to the right people at the right time, right format, and at the right cost (APQC). So they can act more efficiently and effectively to create value for the organization. Therefore, it consists of initiatives, strategies, processes and systems that support storage, assessment, participation, and knowledge creation (Jashapara, 2011).
- Resources management: Resources management is the process by which businesses manage their various resources in the most efficient and effective way. These resources include intangible – people and time – and tangible resources such as equipment, materials, and finances (Business encyclopedia).

Electronic of human resources management closely related to organizational excellence, in light of the rapid economic, organizational, technological and cognitive changes in the current era, the rapid and astonishing development of ICT and its uses in various economic fields have given business organizations opportunities and great challenges. In light of this situation, a fundamental question arises as to how closed and self-absorbed business organizations, which are affected by an inappropriate economic environment, can rely on their human resources to manage their assets and achieve excellence.

Therefore human resources that depends on technology in their work are considered an important element in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization in managing its functions and activities as an outcome of the organization's own efficiency and effectiveness and its ability to achieve organizational excellence. All this is achieved if the best selection and recruitment of qualified competencies, and then carefully planned and cared for, maintained and developed, and a fair system of salaries, bonuses and incentives and the adoption of objectivity in the promotion decisions in accordance with fair considerations and standards that are clear and transparent.

As a result, electronic applications, including electronic human resources management, play an effective role in fulfilling the requirements of achieving excellence. It enables managing the organization's tangible and intangible assets with high efficiency, which has earned electronic human resources management of great importance, and changed the nature of its work and operations through relying on new technology and electronic applications. This requires a non-traditional qualifications for various functions, including functions and activities related to human resources management from planning, recruitment, selection, appointment and others. In light of the above, the key role played by human resources department in the organizations is to provide the necessary labor with competence and specialization, who will be responsible for achieving excellence. As well as to carry out many tasks and responsibilities related to human resource functions such as planning, attracting and training, and establishing a system of wages, rewards and fair incentives and evaluating their performance which must be supported electronically through electronic human resource management applications. Hence, the relationship between electronic human resources management and organizational excellence.

4. Related Studies

(Paul & Michelle 2017) "Electronic human resource management: Enhancing or entrancing?" The purpose of this paper was to determine the link between E-HRM and organizational productivity, and found the notion of the implementation of E-HRM will lead to improved organizational productivity commonly assumed; but empirical evidence in this regard found to be limited.

(Madadha & Kasasba, 2016) in his study aimed to measure the impact of e-management in achieving the competitive advantages of Clearance Companies in Jordan. The study found that there is a statistically significant impact of electronic human resources in innovation. However, there is no impact of electronic devices and electronic programs in innovation. There is also a statistically significant impact of human resources and electronic programs on the service quality.

(Shuai, Ahlam, 2016). Study the impact of e-management on the development and improvement of performance (size, speed, simplicity and quality), the study found that e-management is a new type of management that has brought about profound changes in the management environment in various social organizations and has enabled it to provide better services to beneficiaries and better performance for employees. As well as a significant, shift in traditional management functions in terms of planning, organizing, leadership and controlling. Through the restructuring of administrative procedures, the reallocation of functions and powers, and the delegation of authority.

(Kharroub, 2016) The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of E-Business capabilities on the performance of human resources and organizational performance in Jordanian retail sector a case study on Sameh Mall Investment Group. The study results showed that Sameh Mall Investment Group is highly implementing E-Business capabilities for leveraging performance of human resources and organizational performance as a whole.

The study of (Almbaidien, 2013) entitled "Effectiveness of institutional performance assessment system in organizational excellence: an applied study in the Social Security Corporation- Jordan". The study concluded that: A statistically significant impact of the effectiveness of the performance

appraisal system in organizational excellence. It recommended that staff to held workshops to introduce the importance of performance assessment and organizational excellence for organizations.

Study (Al-Azab and Al-Anzi, 2013)The study aimed to determine the impact of human resource management functions on organizational excellence in the Saudi Customs Authority. The study concluded that there is a statistically significant positive impact of the functions of human resources management on organizational excellence in Saudi Customs, and explained (63%) of variance at organizational excellence. It recommended the creation of an organizational culture that promotes the optimal use of human resources functions by harmonizing the analysis and design of work in line with the organizational structure in order to achieve organizational excellence and continuity.

(Mäkinen, 2013) ” Strategic value of electronic human resource management: case financial institution”, This study aimed to analyse the strategic role of E-human resource management in creating value, it is a qualitative research. To achieve this three research questions were formed. Data was collected through a single case face-to-face semi-structured interviews. The study found that E-HRM can provide strategic value, which may lead to competitive advantage, if the system’s intended role is understood and clarified to employees.

(Sadiq, 2012) “The impact of information systems on the performance of human resources department”. The study aimed at identifying the extent of using HRIS to improve the administrative and strategic functions of human resources management in the private sector companies in Lahore- Pakistan. The study concluded that there is a positive use of the Human Resources Information System (HRIS) as an administrative efficiency tool for adding value in the human resources management departments and the lack of adequate awareness of the strategic benefits of HRIS, which prevents its full utilization.

Study (Abdel Nasser and Al-Qurashi, 2011)Entitled "The contribution of electronic management in the development of work in institutions of higher education - a case study at the Faculty of Science and Commerce, University of Biskra - Algeria"The study concluded that there is a statistically significant impact of the application of electronic management on the quality of work in its different dimensions. It recommended the development of electronic management infrastructure in addition to providing consultants and trainers in this field.

Study (Abuamouna, 2009)The aim of this study is to identify the reality of awareness of electronic human resources management in the public Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip, and to identify the importance of electronic human resources management at different administrative levels. It also aimed to identify the support provided by senior management to help shift to e-management and identification of the infrastructure of IT centers and their readiness to achieve this transformation. The results of the study showed the awareness of the importance of electronic human resources management and senior management support facilitate the process of transition to electronic management. The IT infrastructure has been found to be practically sufficient for this transformation, despite the fact that there is a financial deficit in all universities and the different priorities according to the senior management policy and priorities. As for the university system,

the results showed that there is an application for electronic human resources management in the universities sample of the study.

The previous studies dealt with the impact of electronic management on multiple variables such as productivity, performance, strategic value, quality of work, While other studies dealt with the impact of different variables in organizational excellence such as: performance appraisal system and human resources management (not electronically). In addition, they applied to different organizations; few were applied on the Social Security Corporation and does not address these variables together. Therefore, this study designed to measure the impact of electronic human resources management in the organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation - Jordan, which distinguished it from other studies and give its originality.

5. Methodology

This study belongs to analytical descriptive studies. It is descriptive in terms of presenting specific and causal characteristics. This approach goes beyond data collection and description of phenomena to the analysis and derivation of meaningful conclusions regarding the problem addressed by the research and the effect of the independent variable on the dependent.

5.1. Problem Statement

How to sustain competitive advantage at the changing global economy becomes the most important issue in today's, on the other hand technology is changing very fast; one of these new technologies is electronic human resource management applications. These applications of electronic human resource management are becoming popular among all organizations in all types small, medium, and large organizations, private and public, but still our public organizations don't aware the benefits of using electronic human resource management applications in their work and how to exploit this technology to gain a sustainable strategic added value to achieve organizational excellence. Actuarial studies (2015) also indicate that the Social Security Corporation faces a major challenge in its future, as a result of the increase in the proportion of pensioners and beneficiaries compared to the proportion of subscribers, and the low return on investments managed by the institution (Actuarial study 8, 2015). Where the figures in the annual report for 2016 indicate the retirement pension is (200,000), (46.1%) of them, in average in the early retirement, where in year (2016); they were (61%) of the total retirees for the same year and it is increasing annually. This causes the suspension of contributions from them and the receipt of pensions instead, knowing that most of them raise his salary under the guarantee in the past five years, the years subject to the guarantee, and the average age for them is (50) year. Which is the age of the payment of salaries for many years within the life span of human beings, the average age of the total retirees decreases according to the report also, for example, from (52) in (2015) to (51) in (2016). The Fund's investment fund assets increased from (4.5) billion JD in (2008) to (8.325) in (2016) with a profit of JD (315.1) million. Which is a small figure (3.7%) compared to the size of assets of the largest investment fund in the Kingdom, which hoped to be reliable on improving the status of the institution and moving the economy in general. All this puts the institution in front of future challenges that require it to excel in its work. Research on this topic and explores electronic human resource management applications and their effect on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation is very important to survive in serving its

subscribers and invest their savings effectively, and hence came the problem of study. Therefore, the problem of the study is to answer the following main question:

What is the impact of the use of electronic human resources management in achieving organizational excellence in the Social Security Corporation - Jordan?

5.2. Importance of the Study

This study attempts to shed light on the electronic human resources management, its benefits, its challenges, and the role it plays in achieving organizational excellence in the Social Security Corporation - Jordan. The study is also according to the researcher's knowledge one of the few studies that dealt with this subject in one of the most important institutions responsible for the future of a wide segment of the Jordanian people. It tries to know the level of use of electronic human resources management and the exploitation of advanced technology in the institution, especially in the management of the human resource to deal with developments and expand its work in an unstable environment suffer from difficult economic conditions. If we know the significant role played by this institution in managing and investing the huge amounts of money collected from a wide range of subscribers to ensure their future, where the assets of the Social Security Corporation more than (9) billion Jordanian dinars, of which (8.325) billion dinars in the investment fund as noted above. Therefore, legislations should be developed and studies should be conducted to manage the these huge assets to ensure this in light of the erosion of citizens' incomes and the difficult economic conditions prevailing in the Middle East in general and Jordan In particular.

Therefore, such a study may contribute to opening new horizons to the Social Security Corporation - Jordan through the applications of modern technology, especially electronic human resources management and its role in achieving organizational excellence. In order to survive and grow if we know the enormous potential offered by advanced technology in making the human resource capital real important and strategic partner asset of the institution.

The results of this study expected to benefit the Social Security Corporation in knowing the strengths and weaknesses in the applications of human resources management. In addition, how to exploit electronic human resources management in developing work. Helping them also to understand how to achieve organizational excellence through electronic human resources management and well manage people savings in a dynamic changing complex environment.

5.3. Study Objectives

The main purpose of this study is to find out the role of electronic human resource management applications on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation– Jordan.

This study aims to:

- Find out the level of using of electronic human resource management applications at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.
- Find out the level of organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation– Jordan.
- Explore the role of exploiting electronic human resource management applications on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.
- Give recommendations to Social Security Corporation and other organizations.

5.4. Hypothesis

The first main hypothesis of the study: There is a significant positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of electronic human resource management on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

Minor hypothesis are:

P1: There is a positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of E- planning on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

P2: There is a positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of E- selection& recruitment on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

P3: There is a positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of E- compensation on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

P4: There is a positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of E- learning& development on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

P5: There is a positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of E- performance management on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

The second main hypothesis of the study: There is a significant positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of electronic human resource management on each dimension of organizational excellence (process management, project management, change management, knowledge management, and resources management) *individually* at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

Figure 1: Study model - Electronic human resource management applications and its effect on organizational excellence

Source: Researcher depending on sources

5.5. The limits of the Study

- Spatial boundaries: Social Security Corporation - Jordan.
- Time Limits: The study conducted during the period from August until December 2017.
- Objective Limits: Electronic human resources management and its effect on organizational excellence.

5.6. Procedural Definitions

Electronic human resource management: Is a unique application of web-based technologies in HR-related systems in all human resource functions (HR planning, selection and recruitment, learning and development, compensation, and performance evaluation). That will contribute, together with other organizational changes, to broad access to human resources information as well as to provide multiple opportunities for managing such information for the purposes of achieving organizational excellence.

Organizational excellence: ability of the organization in dealing with its problems and managing its activities effectively and efficiently depending on new electronic applications in way other organizations cannot do.

Social Security Corporation: Social security is a general social insurance Jordanian Corporation established to protect people socially and economically under the law. Responsible for collecting subscriptions from subscribers, and manage these money to performs benefits in the event of a social hazard such as old age, disability, Death, work injury, unemployment, etc. These benefits financed from contributions paid by insured persons and employers and managed b. This system is concerned with the achievement of considerations of social sufficiency.

5.7. Data Collection

Depending on (Harrington, 2004) (Malawi, 2017) and others. Researcher developed a questionnaire. A content validity done by two different groups. The first one contained expert people working in Social Security Corporation- Jordan; and the second group are faculty members, whose major related to E-management and organizational excellence.

Next, result items ordered randomly for each construct. The Likert (1-5) scale used, the mean is judged as low if mean is (1 to < 2.34), moderate if mean (≥ 2.34 and < 3.67), and high if mean > 3.67, and all items tested using Cronbach's alpha, table (1) below shows results. The results obtained indicate that the coefficient of constancy of the model in the Cronbach-alpha test for the independent variables EHRM of various types is (0.78), and in the variables of the dependent variable organizational excellence combined is (0.83). For the entire instrument is (0.78), which is greater the minimum level of independency (0.70) (Hair et al., 2010), therefor the instrument is reliable and can be generalized.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Variables	Reliability
E- planning	0. 76
E- selection& recruitment	0. 74

E- compensation	0.81
E- learning& development	0.84
E- performance management	0.71
E-HRM	0.78
Process management	0.81
Project management	0.86
Change management	0.73
Knowledge management	0.71
Resources management	0.82
Organizational excellence	0.79
Total	0.78

It also planned to conduct a number of interviews to obtain field data from related persons in the real work. However, this was not complete, because most of the sample did not respond for different reasons, forcing the researcher to rely on the questionnaire as the sole source of field data collection besides some data from Social Security Corporation reports.

5.8. Sample

A stratified random sample of (97) person from middle and top management their number is (294) employees was selected for data collection. The number of completed and valid questionnaires received were (82), 63 were male, 19 female; Bachelor or less (BA) 68, and the rest were postgraduate.

6. Results Related to the First and Second Objectives of the Study

- Find out the level of using of electronic human resource management applications at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.
- Find out the level of organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation– Jordan.

To achieve this, the researcher extracted the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study tool areas, as shown in the following table:

Table 2: Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study areas

#	Area	Average	Standard Deviation
1	E- planning	3.64	0.84
2	E- selection& recruitment	3.81	0.66
3	Electronic compensation	3.76	0.92
4	E- learning& development	4.03	0.72
5	E- performance management	3.54	0.59
	Electronic human resource management	3.76	
6	Process management	4.02	0.63
7	Project management	3.92	0.76
8	Change management	3.87	0.68
9	Knowledge management	4.08	0.84

10	Resources management	3.95	0.53
Organizational Excellence		3.97	

We can see from the above table that the averages for all areas of study are high except using E-performance management, which comes at a moderate level with an arithmetic mean (3.54). The highest arithmetic average for – Knowledge management (4.08). In addition, the total mean related to electronic human resource management is (3.76) which is moderately high and this result is copatable with (Abuoamouna, 2009), and for Organizational Excellence (3.97) which is high and compatible partially with (Karoub, 2016). This result indicated the interest of Social Security Organization in integrating electronic applications in human resource management to achieve excellence in its work.

Prior the regression analysis we examined for the normal distribution of the data, Multicollinearity issue, and the internal consistency of the variables to confirm the quality of data. We estimated the data Skewness and Kurtosis to assess the normality of data. As shown in table (3), the values of Skewness and Kurtosis for each variable are less than the threshold of absolute value of (3). This suggests that our data is normally distributed (Hair et al., 2010). For Multicollinearity issue, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is a frequently used to inspect Multicollinearity. According to the rule of thumb, a VIF value of (5) and higher indicates a potential problem of Multicollinearity(Hair et al., 2010). The results presented in table (3) show that the VIF values vary between (1.17 and 2.65) which less than the cut-off value of (5). Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed path model has no Multicollinearity issue. Table (3) Skewness and Kurtosis analysis.

Table 1: Skewness, Kurtosis, and VIF of all variables

Variable name	Skewness		Kurtosis		VIF	Tolerance
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error		
Total Electronic human resource management	-.487	.273	.363	.548	1.176	.750
Total organizational excellence	-.556	.276	.582	.546	1.186	.750
E- planning	-.351	.274	-.643	.546	1.824	.532
E- selection& recruitment	-.667	.287	.999	.546	2.243	.443
Electronic compensation	-.548	.287	.581	.551	1.732	.437
E- learning& development	-.430	.275	.512	.532	2.650	.366
E- performance management	-.481	.283	.344	.522	1.472	.674
Process management	-.812	.281	.859	.543	2.146	.491
Project management	-.540	.283	.636	.531	1.935	.438
Change management	-.492	.281	.314	.528	1.476	.585
Knowledge management	-.811	.277	.929	.544	2.135	.492
Resources management	-.550	.281	.525	.534	1.942	.527

6.1. This Part Including the Hypotheses Testing Results

Main general hypotheses: There is a significant positive effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of electronic human resource management on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

To examine our hypotheses we run six models. In the first model, we examine the main hypothesis, which predicts a positive and significant relationship between EHRM and organizational excellence. In the second model, we examine the effect of each dimension of EHRM including E-planning, E- selection& recruitment, Electronic compensation, E- learning& development, and E-performance management on overall organizational excellence. Finally, in the last three models we examined the effect of overall EHRM on each dimension of organizational excellence including Process management, Project management, Change management, Knowledge management, and Resources management.

As shown in table 4, the result of the first model indicates that EHRM as a whole explains about 0.49 ($R^2=0.49$) of the variance in the organizational excellence as a whole and the F-test is significant at ($p < 0.00$). This suggests that EHRM as a whole have a significant impact on organizational excellence as a whole. The sign of the EHRM's standardized coefficient is positive. This suggests that the relationship is positive and significant at $P < 0.05$. This result offers a sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative. Therefore, the main hypothesis in this study is fully accepted, which is indicated and assures the role of electronic human resource management applications in achieving organizational excellence which is compatible partially with (Paul&Mickell, 2017).

Table 4: Result of OLS regression between the overall EHRM and the overall organizational excellence

Model	F test	R ²	standardized coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)				5.693	.001
Overall organizational Justice	15.284**	0.49	.558	8.677	.001

*** signifies significant at 0.00

The result of the second model, which examines the effect of each dimension of EHRM on organizational excellence as whole, is presented in table (5). The overall F-test is significant at ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the dimensions of E-HRM are significant jointly. The model explains about 0.76 as reflected by R2 value. Individually, the result shows that the standardized coefficients (Beta) of E-planning, E- selection& recruitment, and E- performance management are not significant at $p < 0.05$. This indicates that E- planning, E- selection& recruitment, and E-performance management individually have no effect on organizational excellence as a whole. This suggests that any increases in those variables have no corresponding increases in organizational excellence. Accordingly, we fail to accept the minor hypotheses from the first main hypotheses that P1) E-planning, P2) E- selection& recruitment, and P5) E- performance management have positive effect on organizational excellence.

On the other hand, the standardized coefficient of E-compensation and E- learning& development are positive and significant (coefficient= 0.135, 0.708, $P < 0.036$, 0.0001) respectively. This suggests that as E-compensation and E- learning& development increase, organizational excellence increase. Thus, we have a sufficient evidence to accept P3) and P4) from the first main hypotheses that predicts a positive relationship between E-compensation, E- learning& development and organizational excellence.

Table 5: Results of Multiple regression between E-HRM and organizational excellence

Independent variables	Beta	T	T Sig.	R	R Square	F	F Sig.
Regression constant	0.196	0.665	0.508	0.869	0.756	38.629	0.001
E-planning	0.037	0.109	0.914				
E- selection& recruitment	0.504	1.683	0.097				
E-compensation	0.135	2.140	0.036				
E- learning& development	0.708	7.168	0.0001				
E- performance management	0.223	1.611	0.111				

Dependent Variable: organizational excellence

Finally, the effect of overall EHRM on each dimension of organizational excellence including, *process management, project management, change management, knowledge management, and resources management* is reported in table (6). As shown in table 6, the association between EHRM as whole and organizational excellence dimensions is positive and significant as follows respectively (coefficient= 0.37, 0.27, 0.32, 0.34, 0.32 and sig. at $P < 0.01$). The overall model is also significant for each dimension of organizational excellence (F test is significant at $P < 0.01$) and it explains about (0.42, 0.20, 0.25, 0.22, 0.40) of the variance in each dimension of organizational excellence respectively. These figures provide sufficient information to accept the second main hypothesis that is there is a positive relationship between EHRM as a whole and the dimensions of organizational excellence including, process management, project management, change management, knowledge management, and resources management *individually*.

Table 6: Results of Simple Regression Relationship Between electronic human resource management and organizational excellence indicators

dependent variables	Beta	T	Sig.	R	R ²	F	Sig.	Acceptance
H1: process management	0.37	3.78	0.00	0.65	0.42	10.30	0.00	Accepted
H2: project management	0.27	2.72	0.01	0.45	0.20	3.96	0.00	Accepted
H3: change management	0.32	3.25	0.00	0.50	0.25	8.14	0.01	Accepted
H4: knowledge management	0.34	3.44	0.01	0.47	0.22	6.77	0.00	Accepted
H5: Resources management	0.32	3.30	0.00	0.63	0.40	6.77	0.00	Accepted

Independent: electronic human resource management

7. Results

- The level of electronic human resource management at Social Security Corporation- Jordan is high with arithmetic mean (3.76).
- The level of organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan also high with arithmetic mean (3.97).
- There is significant effect of electronic human resource management as a whole on organizational excellence at Social Security Corporation- Jordan, which interpreted (0.49) of variance in organizational excellence.
- E-compensation and E- learning& development variables also affect organizational excellence individually, whereas E-planning, E- selection& recruitment, and E-performance management are not significant at $p < 0.05$, means they have no effect individually on organizational excellence.

- There is significant effect of electronic human resource management as a whole on each organizational excellence variable (process management, project management, change management, knowledge management, and Resources management).

8. Discussion and Implications

I believe that public organizations in general; and Social Security Corporation- Jordan in particular now a days realize the role of electronic human resource management in the new business, and adopt organizational excellence as necessity for survival and continuity in serving people. Clear understanding and alignment of electronic human resource management for organizational excellence is essential to realize the potential benefits to Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

In this study, i examined the effect of independent variable (electronic human resource management) on the dependent variable (organizational excellence with its variables) in Social Security Corporation- Jordan. I presented an initial implementation of electronic human resource management applications for Social Security Corporation. These applications are to be seen as an important step towards a high support for organizational excellence in all its variables.

The findings of this study indicate that electronic human resource management applications used with high level at Social Security Corporation – Jordan except E- performance management, which comes at a moderate level, organizational excellence also high. There is a significant positive effect of electronic human resource management on organizational excellence in all its variables. Social Security Corporation- Jordan aware of the benefits, which can be obtained once they use electronic human resource management applications. Furthermore, they were convinced if they adopted electronic human resource management, it will give them a competitive edge and survival for future. On the other hand, the corporation realize the role of organizational excellence in today's business.

Therefore, the first implication of this study is that electronic human resource management is the key to success in organizational excellence in all its indicators; this would lead to facilitate electronic human resource management adoption successfully. Secondly, because expected benefits have a positive effect on the adoption of electronic human resource management, Social Security Corporation- Jordan should convert those opportunities into reality and maximize exploiting electronic human resource management tools in achieving organizational excellence, in order to ensure fruitful results alongside the shift towards electronic human resource management. Thirdly, because of survival and competitive pressures, Social Security Corporation should take into consideration that electronic human resource management and organizational excellence adoption would reinforce the company position and give it a competitive advantage. In order to exploit this opportunity, they have to go forward to expand using electronic human resource management and aware people about benefits of this strategy adoption, and this is the main implication of this study.

From the entire researcher can say; the originality of this research comes from studying an important issue whether better assimilation of organizational excellence can exist triggered by the electronic human resource management adoption. It is unique in its broad analysis of its related terms – electronic human resource management and organizational excellence - in an important corporation responsible for people future, which is Social Security Corporation- Jordan.

9. Limitations of the Study

This study faces many limitations such as:

- Some employees do not response effectively to the study.
- Branches of the company spread in all the country.

10. Directions for Future Research

Following my research model, future research can be conducted at Social Security Corporation-Jordan and other institutions or sectors (government institutions, health, education, and so forth), after a while to determine their developments in adoption of electronic human resource management for organizational excellence. For organizational excellence, different indicators may be used for future research to investigate the real effect on organizations excellence.

Appendix 1: tool of the study

No.	Item
Electronic human resource management applications (EHRM)	
E-planning for human resources	
1.	EHRM applications provide clear information on the stock of human skills and experiences in the Social Security Corporation.
2.	Electronic applications contribute in job analysis and provide functional descriptions of each job and the characteristics of its occupant.
3.	Electronic applications determine the future needs of the organization's from human resources
E-selection and recruitment	
4.	The criteria used for the selection and recruitment of employees are credible and consistent
5.	Electronic applications provide data about vacancies in the corporation.
6.	Electronic applications work to sort, and categorize applications for employment.
7.	Electronic applications provide a wider geographical area for employee selection.
8.	Electronic applications contribute to placing the right person in the right place and in accordance with the specialization and experience.
9.	EHRM applications enhance the efficiency and integrity of the selection process.
E-compensation	
10.	EHRM help in gathering, processing, analyzing, and store compensation data in the corporation.
11.	EHRM provide compensation dataand access to anyone at anytime
12.	EHRM in achieving fairness compensation to employees.
E-learning and development	
13.	Electronic applications provide the data and information necessary to plan and implement training programs according to the needs of the organization
14.	Electronic applications help determine the costs of training programs
15.	Electronic applications facilitate the process of evaluating the results of programs and training courses conducted by the corporation for employees
16.	Electronic applications facilitate tele-training
17.	Electronic applications provide monitoring mechanisms that ensure effective training.
E-performance evaluation	

18.	EHRM provides impartial and fair standards in evaluating employee performance
19.	EHRM provides accurate information on the level of performance of employee that help make the right decisions about promotion and reward
20.	EHR enable collective and individual assessment.
21.	EHRM provides information on the performance of each employee to identify weaknesses and strengths and make plans about this.
Organizational excellence	
Business processes management	
22.	EHRM save a lot of time and effort in business processes
23.	EHRM contributes at minimizing human errors.
24.	EHRM increases the productivity and efficiency of employees
25.	EHRM improves the quality of services provided
26.	EHRM provides more accurate and timely reporting on the organization's operations
Project management	
27.	EHR applications help to segment project tasks and activities among employees.
28.	EHRM facilitates the control of various projects at all stages.
29.	EHRM applications contribute to improving the quality of projects
Change management	
30.	EHRM facilitates the organization's orientations in changing organizational culture
31.	EHRM facilitates a change in the corporation's organizational structure
32.	EHRM enables easy change of tasks
33.	EHRM facilitates the change and absorption of the technology used
Knowledge management	
34.	EHRM facilitates the process of acquiring knowledge
35.	EHRM helps generate knowledge
36.	EHRM helps in knowledge storage.
37.	EHRM contributes to the dissemination of knowledge
38.	EHRM helps in knowledge Application
Resources management	
39.	EHRM facilitates the management of data and information resources
40.	EHRM facilitates the control of financial and material resources
41.	EHRM helps manage various assets within the corporation.

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